

5.5 Dimension数据的可视化分析

李杰博士 陈超美教授

中国科学院 文献情报中心
美国德雷塞尔大学 计算与信息学院
lijie_jerry@126.com

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

Dimension. ai

- <https://www.dimensions.ai/>

Dimensions

DIMENSIONS FOR ABOUT DIMENSIONS WORKING TOGETHER RESOURCES CONTACT US

Linked research data from idea to impact

Dimensions data and solutions for discovery and analytics

ACCESS FREE WEB APP

RESEARCHERS CORPORATE R&D PUBLISHERS GOVERNMENT & FUNDERS ACADEMIC PHARMA

The world's largest linked research information dataset

128m Publications	12m Datasets	743k Policy	146m Patents
----------------------	-----------------	----------------	-----------------

Dimension. ai

Dimensions

DOCUMENTS

Search in: Full data Title and abstract DOI

43,335 1,538 835 34 3 27

Show abstract Sort by: Relevance

Title, Author(s), Bibliographic reference - [About the metrics](#)

Academic Publication of Anesthesiology From a Bibliographic Perspective From 1999 to 2018: Comparative Analysis Using Subject-Field Dataset and Department Dataset
Sy-Yuan Chen, Ling-Fang Wei, Mu-Hsuan Huang, Chiu-Ming Ho
2021, *Frontiers in Medicine* - Article
Background: Publication activity in the field of anesthesiology informs decisions that enhance academic advancement. Most previous bibliometric studies on anesthesiology examined data limited t... [more](#)

Exploring Topics in Bibliometric Research Through Citation Networks and Semantic Analysis
Cristian Mejia, Mengjia Wu, Yi Zhang, Yuya Kajikawa
2021, *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics* - Article
This article surveys topic distributions of the academic literature that employs the terms bibliometrics, scientometrics, and informetrics. This exploration allows informing on the adoption of those t... [more](#)
 2 6

Neurodegenerative Diseases and Cholesterol: Seeing the Field Through the Players
Frank W. Pfrieder
2021, *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience* - Article
Neurodegenerative diseases, namely Alzheimer's (AD), Parkinson's (PD), and Huntington's disease (HD) together with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and multiple sclerosis (MS), devas... [more](#)
 2 12

FILTERS FAVORITES

GROUPS

MY GROUPS

Create a group by selecting multiple entities from one of the filters and click 'Add to group' at the bottom.

FUNDER GROUPS **Metaverse***

RESEARCH ORGANIZATION GROUPS

PUBLICATION YEAR

RESEARCHER

FUNDER

COUNTRY OF FUNDER

RESEARCH ORGANIZATION

LOCATION - RESEARCH ORGANIZATION

RESEARCH CATEGORIES

PUBLICATION TYPE

SOURCE TITLE

PUBLICATIONS 851 DATASETS 3 GRANTS 22 PATENTS 122 CLINICAL TRIALS 4 POLICY DOCUMENTS 0

Show abstract Sort by: Relevance

Title, Author(s), Bibliographic reference - [About the metrics](#)

Microwave-Assisted Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles for Multimode Colorimetric Sensing of Multiplex Metal Ions and Molecular Informatization Applications

Min Xia Quan, Qing Feng Yao, Qing Yu Liu, Zhen Qi Bu, Xue Zhi Ding, Li Qiu Xia, Jiao Yang Lu, Wei Tao Huang

2022, ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces - Article

Plasmonic materials have been widely used in chemo/biosensing and biomedicine. However, little attention has been paid to the application of plasmonic materials in terms of the transition from molecu... [more](#)

Citations 2 Altmetric 10 [Add to Library](#)

Towards Aircraft Maintenance Metaverse Using Speech Interactions with Virtual Objects in Mixed Reality

Aziz Siyaev, Geun-Sik Jo

2021, Sensors - Article

Metaverses embedded in our lives create virtual experiences inside of the physical world. Moving towards metaverses in aircraft maintenance, mixed reality (MR) creates enormous opportunities for the i... [more](#)

Citations 10 [View PDF](#) [Add to Library](#)

Utilizing the Metaverse for Learner-Centered Constructivist Education in the Post-Pandemic Era: An Analysis of Elementary School Students

Woong Suh, Seongjin Ahn

2022, Journal of Intelligence - Article

Due to COVID-19, numerous new technologies are being implemented in education, with a growing interest in the metaverse. The term "metaverse" refers to an immersive digital environment where one can i... [more](#)

Citations 1 [View PDF](#) [Add to Library](#)

An All-In-One Multifunctional Touch Sensor with Carbon-Based Gradient Resistance Elements

Chao Wei, Wansheng Lin, Shaofeng Liang, Mengjiao Chen, Yuanjin Zheng, Xinqin Liao, Zhong Chen

2022, Nano-Micro Letters - Article

HighlightsCarbon-based gradient resistance element structure is proposed for the construction of multifunctional touch sensor,

结果导出：
点击页面中Save/Export

Export results

Export full record

File format: Excel - XLSX ▾

Export for bibliometric mapping

File includes data to create bibliometric networks with [VOSviewer ↗](#) or [CiteSpace ↗](#)

Export for reference manager

File format: BibTeX ▾

All items - max 5,000 items per download

Send email when export is ready

Processing the export can take several hours depending on size of the download and system activity. Your export will be available in the [Export center ↗](#) for 30 days.

Cancel

Export

选择 Export for
bibliometric mapping

Your export is now being processed and will be available in the [Export center](#) when ready. Note: At peak times exports may take several hours depending on system activity.

Dimension

Export center

The screenshot displays the Dimensions database interface. At the top, the search criteria are 'DOCUMENTS metaverse*' with a sub-filter 'Free text in title and abstract'. The user 'Jie Lie' is logged in. The main content area shows a list of publications under the 'PUBLICATIONS' tab, with 851 results. Three publications are visible:

- 1** [Microwave-Assisted Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles for Multimode Colorimetric Sensing of Multiplex Metal Ions and Molecular Informatization Applications](#)
Min Xia Quan, Qing Feng Yao, Qing Yu Liu, Zhen Qi Bu, Xue Zhi Ding, Li Qiu Xia, Jiao Yang Lu, Wei Tao Huang
2022, ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces - Article
Plasmonic materials have been widely used in chemo/biosensing and biomedicine. However, little attention has been paid to the application of plasmonic materials in terms of the transition from molecu... more
Citations: 2, Altmetric: 10, Add to Library
- [Towards Aircraft Maintenance Metaverse Using Speech Interactions with Virtual Objects in Mixed Reality](#)
Aziz Siyaev, Geun-Sik Jo
2021, Sensors - Article
Metaverses embedded in our lives create virtual experiences inside of the physical world. Moving towards metaverses in aircraft maintenance, mixed reality (MR) creates enormous opportunities for the i... more
Citations: 10, View PDF, Add to Library
- [Utilizing the Metaverse for Learner-Centered Constructivist Education in the Post-Pandemic Era: An Analysis of Elementary School Students](#)
Woong Suh, Seongjin Ahn
2022, Journal of Intelligence - Article
Due to COVID-19, numerous new technologies are being implemented in education, with a growing interest in the metaverse. The term "metaverse" refers to an immersive digital environment where one can i... more
Citations: 1, View PDF, Add to Library

The right sidebar shows an 'ANALYTICAL' section with a line graph of 'Publications (total)' from 2013 to 2022. The graph shows a sharp increase in 2022. Below the graph is an 'OVERVIEW' section with a table of Open Access (OA) levels:

Open Access Level	Count
Closed	468
All OA	383
Gold	140
Green	138
Bronze	57

A user profile dropdown menu is open for 'Jie Lie', showing options: 'My account', 'Connect with ORCID', 'Export center' (highlighted with a red arrow), and 'Logout'.

Dimension

 Support Jie Lie

Close X

MY ACCOUNT

- General settings
- Set currency
- ORCID information
- Export center**

ABOUT DIMENSIONS

- Dimensions
- About the grants data
- Organization data
- Acknowledgements
- Privacy Policy
- Legal Terms

Export center

Your exports are available to download for 30 days. Note: At peak times exports may take several hours depending on system activity.

Query		↓ Date	Source	Records	File size	Format	
metaverse*	Delete	2022-06-27	Publicati...	851	1 MB	csv (VO...	Download
"climate change"	Delete	2022-06-26	Policy D...	3736	470 kB	xlsx	Download
Metaverse*	Delete	2022-06-24	Publicati...	500	248 kB	xlsx	Download
Metaverse*	Delete	2022-06-24	Publicati...	842	1 MB	csv (VO...	Download
"2019-nCoV" OR "COVID-19" OR "SARS-CoV-2" O...	Delete	2022-06-22	Policy D...	5000	723 kB	xlsx	Download
bibliometric* OR Scientometric* OR informetric*	Delete	2022-06-22	Publicati...	5000	6 MB	xlsx	Download
bibliometric* OR Scientometric* OR informetric*	Delete	2022-06-22	Publicati...	5000	34 MB	csv (VO...	Download

数据下载

Dimension

名称	修改日期	类型	大小
Dimensions-Publication-2022-06-27_09-11-10.csv.zip	2022/6/27 17:15	Compressed File (Z...	1,077 KB

名称	修改日期	类型	大小
download_1-851.csv	2022/6/27 9:11	Microsoft Excel 逗...	2,641 KB
Dimensions-Publication-2022-06-27_09-11-10.csv	2022/6/27 9:11	Microsoft Excel 逗...	2,641 KB
Dimensions-Publication-2022-06-27_09-11-10.csv.zip	2022/6/27 17:15	Compressed File (Z...	1,077 KB

名称	修改日期	类型	大小
data	2022/6/27 17:17	文件夹	
dimension data	2022/6/27 17:17	文件夹	
project	2022/6/27 17:17	文件夹	
Dimensions-Publication-2022-06-27_09-11-10.csv	2022/6/27 9:11	Microsoft Excel 逗...	2,641 KB
Dimensions-Publication-2022-06-27_09-11-10.csv.zip	2022/6/27 17:15	Compressed File (Z...	1,077 KB

CiteSpace

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science Import/Export

Projects

New Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003) More Actions ...

Project Home: C:\Users\dell\citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

Data Directory: C:\Users\dell\citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

GO! Stop Reset JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 11 %

Space Status

Process Reports

Time Slicing

From 1993 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms Detect Bursts Entropy

Node Types

Author Institution Country Term Keyword Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

g-index Top N Top N% Thresholds Citations Usage180 Usage2013

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in Z^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks

Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

CiteSpace: Data Processing Utilities

MySQL WOS Scopus Dimensions CNKI CSSCI MAG CSV PubMed

Search, Download, and Convert Bibliographic Data from Dimensions

1. Search on Dimensions for relevant bibliographic records (e.g., in full data or title/abstract only).
2. Export results with the 'Export for bibliometric mapping' option.
3. You will be notified by email if the export csv file is ready to download.
4. Uncompress the exported file
5. Open the csv file in Notepad++ and remove all "" by replace "" with an empty string.
6. Start the conversion function using the 'Export (csv) -> WoS' button below.

Advanced Functions

Advanced functions such as Cascading Citation Expansion are available in the CiteSpace Advanced version.

You need to obtain a [Dimensions API](#) key from Dimensions in order to use them.

Data Directories

Input Directory Browse

Output Directory Browse

Export (csv) -> WoS DSL + Semmed -> WoS Cascading Citation Expansion A: Database+PubMed B: Files+PubMed

851 records saved from download_1-851.csv.

Total records converted: 851

Dimension → WoS


```
1 PT J
2 AU Wei, C
3   Lin, W
4   Liang, S
5   Chen, M
6   Zheng, Y
7   Liao, X
8   Chen, Z
9 AF Wei, Chao
10  Lin, Wansheng
11  Liang, Shaofeng
12  Chen, Mengjiao
13  Zheng, Yuanjin
14  Liao, Xinqin
15  Chen, Zhong
16 TI An All-In-One Multifunctional Touch Sensor with Carbon-Based
17   Gradient Resistance Elements
18 SO Nano-Micro Letters
19 DT Article
20 AB HighlightsCarbon-based gradient resistance element structure is
21   proposed for the construction of multifunctional touch sensor,
22   which will promote wide detection and recognition range of multiple
23   mechanical stimulations.Multifunctional touch sensor with gradient
24   resistance element and two electrodes is demonstrated to eliminate
25   signals crosstalk and prevent interference during position sensing
26   for human-machine interactions.Biological sensing interface based
27   on a deep-learning-assisted all-in-one multipoint touch sensor
28   enables users to efficiently interact with virtual
29   world.AbstractHuman-machine interactions using deep-learning
30   methods are important in the research of virtual reality, augmented
31   reality, and metaverse. Such research remains challenging as
32   current interactive sensing interfaces for single-point or
33   multipoint touch input are trapped by massive crossover electrodes,
34   signal crosstalk, propagation delay, and demanding configuration
35   requirements. Here, an all-in-one multipoint touch sensor (AIOM
36   touch sensor) with only two electrodes is reported. The AIOM touch
37   sensor is efficiently constructed by gradient resistance elements,
38   which can highly adapt to diverse application-dependent
39   configurations. Combined with deep learning method, the AIOM touch
40   sensor can be utilized to recognize, learn, and memorize
41   human-machine interactions. A biometric verification system is
42   built based on the AIOM touch sensor, which achieves a high
43   identification accuracy of over 98% and offers a promising hybrid
44   cyber security against password leaking. Diversiform human-machine
```

数据分析

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science

Projects

New Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003) More Actions ...

Project Home: C:\Users\dell\.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

Data Directory: C:\Users\dell\.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

GO! Stop Reset JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 11 %

Space Status

Process Reports

Time Slicing

From 1993 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms Detect Bursts Entropy

Node Types

Author Ins

Reference

Links

Stre

Selection Criteria

g-index Top N

The sele

To include mo

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder

Minimum Spa

New Project

Title To compute uncertainties, use the same project name in MySQL as well.

Project Home Browse

Data Directory Browse

Data Source WoS Scopus Lens MAG CNKI/WanFang CSCD CSSCI PubMed

Preferred Language English Chinese

SO Filter: SC Filter:

Alias List (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>	Exclusion List (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>
Export Space (on/off)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Export Abstracts (Time Consuming) (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>
Export Matrices (csv) (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Enable JDIC (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>
Save Merged Slice (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Phrase/Keyword: Minimum Words (2)	<input type="text" value="2"/>
Phrase/Keyword: Maximum Words (4)	<input type="text" value="4"/>	Burst Term Threshold (0.00)	<input type="text" value="0.00"/>
Maximum GML Node Label Length (8)	<input type="text" value="8"/>	CTSA (1-Disciplines, 2-Sciences) (1)	<input type="text" value="1"/>
Include GP (Group Author) (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Include ED (Editors) (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>
Node Degree Weighted (true)	<input type="text" value="true"/>	Look Back Years (LBV)(-1:unlimited)	<input type="text" value="-1"/>
Link Retaining Factor (LRF)(*N; -1:unlimited)	<input type="text" value="3"/>	Percentage of Nodes to Label (%)	<input type="text" value="1.0"/>
Maximum Links Per Node (L/N) (-1:unlimited)	<input type="text" value="10"/>	TopN = {n f(n)>e}	<input type="text" value="1.0"/>
Filter Refs By Intrinsic Citations	<input type="text" value="on"/>	Concept Tree Home	<input type="text" value="C:\Users\cc345\.citespace"/>
Use Authors' Fullnames	<input type="text" value="on"/>	Dimensions Endpoint	<input type="text" value="https://app.dimensions.ai/"/>

Normalize Citations Global Check

Description

Title Metaverse

To compute uncertainties, use the same project name in MySQL as well.

Project Home D:\桌面\Dimension\project

Browse

Data Directory D:\桌面\Dimension\data

Browse

Data Source WoS Scopus Lens MAG CNKI/WanFang CSCD CSSCI PubMedPreferred Language English Chinese

SO Filter:

Enable

Disable

SC Filter:

Enable

Disable

Alias List (on/off) on

Export Space (on/off) off

Export Matrices (csv) (off/on) off

Save Merged Slice (off/on) off

Phrase/Keyword: Maximum Words (4) 4

Maximum GML Node Label Length (8) 8

Include GP (Group Author) (off/on) off

Node Degree Weighted (true) true

Link Retaining Factor (LRF)(*N; -1:unlimited) 3

Maximum Links Per Node (L/N) (-1:unlimited) 10

Filter Refs By Intrinsic Citations on

Use Authors' Fullnames on

 Normalize Citations Global Check

Exclusion List (on/off) on

Export Abstracts (Time Consuming) (on/off) on

Enable JDIC (on/off) on

Phrase/Keyword: Minimum Words (2) 2

Burst Term Threshold (0.00) 0.00

CTSA (1-Disciplines, 2-Sciences) (1) 1

Include ED (Editors) (off/on) off

Look Back Years (LBY)(-1:unlimited) -1

Percentage of Nodes to Label (%) 1.0

TopN = {n|f(n) ≥ e} 1.0

Concept Tree Home C:\Users\lcc345\citespace

Dimensions Endpoint https://app.dimensions.ai/

Description How did you create the dataset?

Save

Cancel

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science

Projects

New Metaverse More Actions ...

Project Home: D:\桌面Dimension\project

Data Directory: D:\桌面Dimension\data

GO! Stop Reset JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 11 %

Time Slicing

From 2013 JAN To 2022 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms Detect Bursts Entropy

Node Types

Author Institution Country Term Keyword Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

g-index Top N Top N% Thresholds Citations Usage180 Usage2013

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks

Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Publications (total)	30	15	6	6	9	8	5	15	135	483

CiteSpace

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science

Projects: Metaverse

Project Home: D:\桌面\Dimension\project

Data Directory: D:\桌面\Dimension\data

JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 13 %

Space Status

Pruning configuration:

2013	g=3, k=25	112	28	74 / 74
2014	g=3, k=25	37	27	81 / 93
2015	g=2, k=25	8	8	11 / 11
2016	g=2, k=25	7	7	15 / 15
2017	g=2, k=25	15	15	31 / 31
2018	g=2, k=25	31	26	73 / 73
2019	g=1, k=25	1	1	0 / 0
2020	g=2, k=25	52	26	78 / 84
2021	g=4, k=25	553	34	53 / 53
2022	g=10, k=25	2621	86	258 / 477

Process Reports

Document Types
8510 Article

Distinct references [Valid]: 6456 100.0000%
Distinct references [Invalid]: 0 0.00000%

Parsing Time: 3 seconds
Total Run time: 4 seconds

Merged network: Nodes=254, Links=674
Exclusion List: 0
Network modeling ends at Mon Jun 27 17:33:26 CST 2022.

Time Slicing
From 2013 JAN To 2022 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source
 Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type
 Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Node Types
 Author Institution Country Term Keyword Source Category
 Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links
Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria
g-index Top N Top N% Thresholds Citations Usage180 Usage2013

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in Z^+$
To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pruning
 Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks
 Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

Your Options

? Project Title: Metaverse

Time Frame: 2013-2022
Qualified Records: 1002

How do you like to proceed?

Spotlight Citation/Frequency Burst >>> <<< Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 81

Visible	Count	Central...	Year	Cited References
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.00	2013	Dionisio JDN, 2013, ACM ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.00	2021	Duan H, 2021, PROCEEDI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.00	2017	Nevelsteen KJL, 2017, CO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.00	2017	Choi H, 2017, INTERNATI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.00	2022	Park S, 2022, IEEE ACCE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	10	0.00	2009	Davis A, 2009, JOURNAL ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	9	0.00	2021	Kye B, 2021, JOURNAL O...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2022	Mystakidis S, 2022, ENCY...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	1997	Azuma RT, 1997, PRESE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2019	Flavián C, 2019, JOURNA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2020	Suzuki S, 2020, PROCEEDI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2021	Kim J, 2021, JOURNAL O...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2015	Barry DM, 2015, PROCEEDI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	Siyae A, 2021, SENSORS...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	1981	Fornell C, 1981, JOURNA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2003	Jaynes C, 2003, PROCEE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2018	Falchuk B, 2018, IEEE TE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2013	Kanematsu H, 2013, PRO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2022	Jeon H, 2022, BLOCKCHA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	1992	Steuer J, 1992, JOURNAL ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	1997	Slater M, 1997, PRESENC...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	1995	Milgram P, 1995, PROCE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2009	Bourlakis M, 2009, ELECT...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	1989	Davis FD, 1989, MIS QUA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2021	Sparkes M, 2021, THE NE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2018	Suh A, 2018, COMPUTER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2022	Xi N, 2022, INFORMATION...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2019	Yeh S, 2019, INTERNATIO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2020	Radiani J, 2020, COMPU...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	Liu Z, 2022, INTERNATIO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2003	Podsakoff PM, 2003, JOU...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2018	Ryskeldiev B, 2018, PROC...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2001	Schubert T, 2001, PRESE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2021	Wiederhold BK, 2021, CY...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2019	Alcañiz M, 2019, FRONTIE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	Rospigliosi P, 2022, INTE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2021	Koo H, 2021, JOURNAL O...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2008	Hendaoui A, 2008, IEEE I...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2013	Gadalla E, 2013, JOURNA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2018	Rauschnabel PA, 2018, J...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2020	Han H, 2020, ADVANCES I...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2021	Bolger RK, 2021, RELIGIO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2015	Rehm S, 2015, JOURNAL ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2020	Díaz JEM, 2020, INTERNA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	Nguyen TN, 2022, JMIRX ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2018	Shin D, 2018, COMPUTER...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2007	Parsons TD, 2007, JOUR...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2008	Papagiannidis S, 2008, T...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2011	Márquez IV, 2011, REVIST...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2016	He K, 2016, 2016 IEEE C...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2021	Rauschnabel PA, 2021, IN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2019	Steffen JH, 2019, JOURNA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2008	Wright M, 2008, PROCEE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	Jovanović A, 2022, ELECT...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	Dowling M, 2022, FINAN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2018	Bai C, 2018, RESPIROLO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2012	Anonymou , 2012, ADVAN...

主题词的分析 (Terms co-occurrence analysis)

总结

- CiteSpace可以对dimension数据分析的内容如下：
- 作者合作、文献共被引分析、作者共被引以及期刊共被引分析
- 期刊的双图叠加、关键词的共现、机构、国家或地区的合作分析存在局限。

CiteSpace学习文献

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

声明：该电子课件为《CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化》的配套电子课件，请合理使用。

科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书 丛书主编: 李 杰

CiteSpace: Text mining and Visualization in Scientific Literature (Fourth Edition)

CiteSpace: 科技文本挖掘及可视化 (第四版)

李 杰 陈超美 著

随着信息技术的飞速进步，**可视化**应用越来越普及，今后的学习越来越多地借助各种可视化手段，视觉器官将发挥前所未有的作用。

可视化方式成为主流学习方式后，人类的学习效率将大大提高，有可能带来一场认知革命。

首都经济贸易大学出版社
Capital University of Economics and Business Press

Home History MOOC Books Journals Tools Scholars Gallery Links Metasciences Safemetrics About

Open Scientometrics Learning Platform
开放科学计量学学习平台

科学计量学理论与工具视频 MOOC for Scientometrics Theories and Tools

开放科学计量学视频号

什么是科学计量学 (AI生成)

CiteSpace理论与实践
(主讲人: 陈超美、李杰)
链接1 链接2 链接3

陈超美 科学网博客
点击前往博客 →

李杰 科学网博客
点击前往博客 →

武夷山 科学网博客
(课外学习推荐)
点击前往博客 →

什么是文献计量学?

文献计量学的局限性

库恩的科学革命

什么是文献共被引?

文献计量学与可视化

库恩的常规科学

《自然》150年 引文空间网络

引文分析的历史

第一届MKD珍贵视频

引文索引50年

科学学导论

负责任的科学计量学

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/mooc>

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.